

A PROFILE OF THE SPORTING HABITS OF STUDENTS BETWEEN 10-16 YEARS OLD FROM MAJORCA ISLAND

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Abstract

This article is part of a wider research study about sporting habits which was carried out with young people between 10 and 16 years old from Majorca Island. In this paper we are analyzing what is the profile of Majorcan young athletes by gender, socio-demographic and sport level.

A sample of 4301 boys and girls from Majorca were surveyed. The sample was obtained from multistage sampling. A specifically designed questionnaire was used.

The results obtained in this study confirm a clear regression in physical activity to increment age of males and females. Also noteworthy are the clearly significant differences between men and women in this age group in terms of sports, frequency, and type of sport practiced. The practicing of sport by parents promotes a greater participation in children. Also, gender marks some differences in relation to the practice of sports in these ages.

Key words: Habits, sports practice, physical activity and gender.

Introduction

The increase in sedentary adults is due in large part to a lifestyle that begins in the early stages. The benefits of physical activity on health are based on numerous studies, Dishman, (1985); Blasco, (1994), Shephard (1996); Biddle, Fox, & Boutcher (2000). Epidemiological research available supports with great uniformity that regular physical activity represents an important health benefit, while its absence is a significant detriment (Varo, Martínez, Martínez, 2003).

According Abarca et al. (2010) recommendations for physical activity for youth are widely used to target an active lifestyle and healthy. Several institutions, including the Ministry of Health of the United Kingdom, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention of the United States and the Ministry of Health and Aging Australia and different experts indicate that children and adolescents should get at least 60 minutes (and up to several hours) of moderate intensity physical activity to intense all or most days of the week.

The latest survey of health habits among the young population of the Community of Madrid, 2009, highlights significant differences between genders. 41.3% of girls and 11.9% of boys do not perform at least three days a week intense physical activity, the survey defined as those whose energy consumption is at least five times higher than the repose. There is a 10% of young people who do not do any physical activity three or more days a week. Women double the proportion of men who confess their inactivity.

AFINOS Research states that the reduction of habitual physical activity has been strengthened as a result of the number of hours children spend sitting in school, using motorized transport to travel and with leisure proliferation of technological inciting to inactivity.

This research highlights the need to intervene on sedentary behaviours to prevent the premature development of cardiovascular risk in childhood and adolescence. Making recommendations is Essentials to reduce time that children and adolescents are inactive. In fact, only 28 percent of Spanish boys and 16 percent of girls between 12 and 17 perform the

recommended amount of physical activity for their age, i.e., 60 minutes of exercise a day at least five days week.

From a wellness-oriented perspective and contribution to personal and social development, we justify that the interest of this research is aimed at discovering generic relationship between Majorca youth and sports, and the factors that determine it, thus identifying the profile of sporting habits according to socio-demographic variables such as gender and age, educational level of parents, socioeconomic status, practice habits of parents. We are also interested to know who and how play sports, the most popular sports, the regular practice, sports facilities used, federated athletes and how to start in sports

From the data and results of other research carried out state-wide Spanish (Escudero et al., 1992; Ponseti, 1998; Palou, 2001; Puig & Campomar, 2003; García-Ferrando, 2006; López del Río, 2006; Palou & Ponseti, 2008) suggested that, at certain ages, it seems that some variables such as gender and socioeconomic status, educational level are determining factors in establishing differences in practice in youth athletes.

In 2006, García-Ferrando, in research on sports practices of the Spanish population between 2000 and 2005, points data on the evolution of the sports habitual practice among them. It concludes that the vast majority of the Spanish population, who play sports, basically makes leisure recreation.

Regarding the variable gender men follow primarily competitive model, and women make a recreational practice. Among the youngest generations, the percentage of the population whose parents do or have done sport is significantly larger than among older generations because of the great importance of sport socialization on the family model.

The aim of this research is to analyse the practice of sports habits in Majorcan youth according to their gender, age, parents sporting habits and their sociocultural and socioeconomic environment. This will be able to diagnose the current situation of the sporting habits of young people in the Balearic Islands and define the strategies needed to promote sports

MATERIAL AND METHOD

SAMPLE

The universe under study of the research is made up of primary and secondary school students of public, private and charter centres, aged between 10 and 16 from Majorca island during 2009-2010 school year (N=47847). The resulting sample was 4301 participants representing 8.9% of the total population of public, private and charter of Majorca.

The final sample was obtained from a multistage sampling rate based on a sample of schools that taught the third cycle of primary and ESO studies, according to the list provided by the Ministry of Education, Government of the Balearic Islands. The resulting mean age was 13.4 years. 51.9% were male and 48.1% female.

QUESTIONNAIRE

The test tool adopted for data collection was a specifically designed questionnaire (Ponseti et al., 1998; Palou, 2001; Palou & Ponseti, 2008), made from the consultation of questionnaires, the 'operationalization' of the variables, the expert consultation and the questionnaire test application. The questionnaire was distributed among the participants of the final sample and shall annex the relevant instructions for its use. All this was realized after obtaining the proper permits from the schools.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Once the subjects completed the questionnaires, the statistical analysis of the collected data was passed to them. To compare qualitative variables, the Chi-square test was used and to compare mean it was used the t-student test and analysis of variance (ANOVA). The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. In those cases where it did not meet the assumptions of normality were used for nonparametric tests. All analyses were performed using SPSS-19 for Windows.

RESULTS

First of all, the data show that a large proportion of young people among 10-16 years old from Majorca practice physical activity outside of physical education classes. We found

that 72.8% of respondents play sports outside of physical education lessons, compared to 27.2% who claims not to do any physical activity outside of school time. In terms of gender differences are noteworthy, such as the claim that men participate in any sports at 80.5% compared to 19.5% who said otherwise. On the other hand, in women 64.5% do practices and 35.5% do not.

It can be seen on Table 1, which refers to the rate of sports practice in terms of socioeconomic status and educational level of parents, that there is a difference between people of low socioeconomic status, with 56.8% of sports habit, respect to persons of other higher levels, with percentages above 70% from middle, upper middle and high. It also shows how the amount of sports practice gradually increases according to the education level of parents. So between people "uneducated" by 61.9% of participants practiced sport and this percentage rises to 80.3% if they have college-educated parents.

As for the hours spent to sports practice outside of physical education classes, the frequency of practice with a 35% majority is among 4 and 8 hours a week. According to gender, men practice during more hours than women, because 38.3% of men practice among 4 and 8 hours, along with 8-12 hours with 30.5%. Women practice mostly 2 and 4 hours 33.6% and 30.6% of 4 to 8 hours. Only 16.9% of women practicing 8-12 hours (see Table 2)

If one studies the level of sports practice related to the sporting habits of parents, it is observed that if parents practice or have practiced sport, the percentages of practitioners increased to 82.7%, otherwise the percentage is 63.1 %. This tendency is broken down by gender as can be seen in Table 3.

Based on the age, 10 years old gets the highest rate of sports practice with 88.5%, decreasing gradually up to 14 years old with 67.9%. According to gender the rate remains highest in Sports practice at 10, but the descent of the girls at age of 14 is amazing with a percentage of 56.9%, meanwhile the boys are kept in 80.8 % in this age group.

The most popular sports are soccer, swimming, basketball, tennis, biking, dancing, hiking, martial arts, skating, gymnastics, skate board, paddle tennis, athletics, football and horse racing. In According to gender differences can be seen on the sports played. The sports which are more neutral: basketball, tennis, cycling, martial arts, hiking and swimming. In males, soccer practice, football, skateboarding and handball. The skate board appears in the last two studies in Ibiza and Majorca as an emerging activity along with the increase of tennis and horse riding. In women highlights the practice of dance, gymnastics, skating and volleyball.

As for with whom play sports 51.3% practice with a team and 29.8% with a group of friends. How do the youth play sports?, mostly as a club activity or as a federation practice 54.9%, and 30% with friends, by gender men increase the percentage of a club to 61.7%.

The regularity of sports practice, 48.5% practiced all year, 34.6% during the school year, by gender, men regular practice increases to 52% and women drop to 43.7 %, during the school year. 30.6% of men practice and 40% of women.

Federated practice is 69%, the gender differences exist because men have a federated percentage of 66.3% and women 44%.

Table 1. Sports practice rates according to the indicator of self-perceived practice, (depending on socioeconomic status and educational level of parents).

	SPORTS PRACTICE		NO SPORTS PRACTICE		Significance
	(N)	%	(N)	%	
	3059	72,9	1136	27,1	
Socioeconomic status					
High	175	78,8	47	21,2	
Medium-high	752	79,3	196	20,7	

Medium	1875	72,1	724	27,9	P<0,001
Medium-low	211	61,2	134	38,8	
Low	46	56,8	35	43,2	
	SPORTS PRACTICE		NO SPORTS PRACTICE		
	(N)	%	(N)	%	
	3006	71,66	1189	28,34	
Parents education level					Significance
No studies	127	61,9	78	38,1	P<0,001
Primary	394	52,2	360	47,8	
Elementary	1039	73,6	372	26,4	
Higher education	596	77,8	170	22,2	
College	850	80,3	209	19,7	

Table 2. Sports practice dedication of weekly hours by gender

	Total		Men		Women		Significance
	(N)	%	(N)	%	(N)	%	
	2447	100	1407	100	1040	100	
Less than 2 hours	319	13	122	8,7	197	18,9	P<0,001
2-4 hours	666	27,2	317	22,5	349	33,6	
4-8 hours	857	35	539	38,3	318	30,6	
8-12 hours	605	24,7	429	30,5	176	16,9	

Table 3. Sports practice rates, according to parents sporting habits.

	CHILDREN WHO PRACTICE SPORTS		CHILDREN WHO DON'T PRACTICE SPORTS		Significance
	(N)	%	(N)	%	
	3123	72,8	1165	27,2	
Father Sports practice					
Father practices	1373	82,1	299	17,9	P<0,001
Father has practiced	700	77,1	208	22,9	
Father has never practiced	1050	61,5	658	38,5	
Mother Sports practice					
Mother practices	1130	83,4	225	16,6	P<0,001
Mother has practiced	570	77,2	168	22,8	
Mother has never practiced	1423	64,8	772	35,2	
Parents Sports practice					
Parents practice	2503	82,7	524	17,3	P<0,001
Parents have practiced	1270	77,2	376	22,8	
Parents have never practiced	2473	63,1	1430	36,9	

DISCUSSION

The main goal is to identify sporting habits of Majorcan youth between 10-16 years old, depending on the variables: gender, age, socioeconomic status, education level of parents and sporting habits of parents.

Highlighting the emergence of significant differences between women and men (10-16 years old) in terms of sports practice, due to the existence of almost twice as many women (35.5%) than men (19.5%) claiming no practice any sports except for school physical education sessions. These results are consistent with data from other similar researches (Blasco, 1994; García-Ferrando, 2004; Puig & Campomar, 2003; Palou & Ponseti, 2008).

Moreover people with medium high and high socioeconomic status are the people who plays sports more, resulting in a decrease in the percentage of practicing it in lower socioeconomic levels

Of note is the fact that sports practice is increased progressively among the population according with the increase of educational level of the parents, these results correspond with sociological studies (Willis and Campbell, 1992; Blasco, 1994; Puig & Campomar, 2003; Palou & Ponseti, 2008).

When it comes to analyze the influence of the sporting habits of parents about their children's sporting habits, as it increases the percentage of parents practice increases the level of engagement of the children sports corroborating data from other researches (García-Ferrando, 1990; Willis and Campbell, 1992; López del Rio, 2006; Palou & Ponseti, 2008).

The highest percentage of age of is 10 years practice, progressively decreasing levels of practice up to 16 years. The decrease in the practice is more pronounced in girls. In the school years where there is greater participation,

as they get older the rate of practitioners' decreases (García-Ferrando, 1990).

From the data obtained on the sports practiced by young people from Majorca there is a trend for men to practice certain sports (soccer, football, skateboarding, handball). Other sports are practiced by girls: dance, gymnastics, volleyball, horse riding, skating and aerobics. The neutral sport is: basketball, tennis, cycling, martial arts, hiking and swimming.

Regarding how to perform sports practice, the most used way to practice is the proposed club and sports federations. Playing sports with their teams and friends, significantly leaving the family aside, has little influence on the people of this age group who are in the habit of sports practice.

Thus, we can define the sportsman profile from Majorca island as a middle-class male, whose parents have a university education and practice or have practiced sport, who spend from 4 to 8 hours a week practicing sports, which are made using a federated team and regularly throughout the school year.

CONCLUSIONS

The results show that gender and age are the most important factors when it comes to sports practice or not.

It is much more likely that a boy or a girl practices sports if their parents practice or have practiced sport.

Increasing the educational level and socioeconomic status, they also increase the levels of sports practice.

The distribution of the different sports activities are not done randomly, following guidelines set by gender, socioeconomic status, education level and family sports practice habits.

The regular practice is closely tied to participate in sports competitions federated.

There is a need to promote sports practice particularly in girls, to prevent a future sedentary lifestyle that may lead to health problems.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Abarca, A., Zaragoza, J., Generelo, E., & Julián, J.A. (2010). Comportamientos sedentarios y patrones de actividad física en adolescentes. *Revista Internacional de Medicina y Ciencias de la Actividad Física y el Deporte*, 10(39), 410-427.
2. Blasco, T. (1994). *Actividad Física y Salud*. Barcelona: Martinez Roca.
3. Biddle, S.J.H., Fox, K.R., & Boutcher, S.H. (2000). *Physical activity and psychological well-being*. London: Routledge.
4. Dishman, R.K. (1985): Mental Health. In V. Seefeldt (ed.), *Physical activity and well-being*. Reston: American Alliance of Health, Physical Education, Recreation and Dance.
5. Escudero, J.T., Serra, F., & Servera, M. (1992). *Estudi dels hàbits esportius de la joventut de les Illes Balears*. Palma: Conselleria de Cultura, Educació i Esports.
6. Garcia-Ferrando, M. (1990). *Aspectos Sociales del Deporte. Una Reflexión Sociológica*. Madrid: Alianza Deporte.
7. García-Ferrando, M. (2004). *Encuesta sobre los hábitos deportivos de los españoles*. Consejo superior de Deportes. Madrid: Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte.
8. García-Ferrando, M. (2006). Posmodernidad y deporte: entre la individualización y la masificación. Encuesta sobre hábitos deportivos de los españoles 2005. Madrid: CIS. CSD.
9. López del Río, A. (2006). *Motius de pràctica esportiva i l'abandó esportiu dels escolars de Menorca entre els 12 i 16 anys*. Consell Insular de Menorca. Maó: Departament de Cooperació Local i esports.
10. Palou, P. (2001). *Hàbits de pràctica esportiva dels Mallorquins entre 10-14 anys*. UIB. Tesi doctoral publicada (www.thesesxarxa.net)
11. Palou, P., & Ponseti, X. (2008). *Habits esportius dels Eivissencs entre 10 i 16 anys*. Eivissa: Consell insular d'Eivissa. Departament de política esportiva i de lleure.
12. Ponseti, X. (1998). Anàlisi de la pràctica esportiva dels joves a Mallorca en el segon cicle d'ESO. UIB. Tesi doctoral no publicada.
13. Puig, N., & Campomar, M.A. (2003). *Hàbits esportius a les Illes Balears. Un estudi sociològic*. Illes Balears: Direcció General d'Esports.
14. Shephard, R. (1996). Habitual physical activity and quality of life. *Quest*, 48, 354-365
15. Varo, J., Martínez, J.A., & Martínez, M.A. (2003). Beneficios de la actividad física y riesgos del sedentarismo. *Medicina Clinica*, 121(17), 665-671.
16. Willis, J.D., & Campbel, L.F. (1992). *Exercice Psychology*, Champaign, Illinois: Human Kinetic.

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